

THE FUNCTIONAL EVIDENCE EVALUATION WORKSHOP 2024

SUMMARY REPORT

Thank you to all that participated in the Functional Evidence Evaluation Workshop!

Summary

Functional evidence can be incorporated into variant classification according to the ACMG/AMP recommendations to support resolving the genetic cause of a condition (Richards et al. 2015, Brnich et al. 2019). Despite its many benefits, functional evidence is one of the least used evidence categories, and remains therefore an untapped resource for resolving uncertainty in diagnostic genomics.

The MAVE Education project recently delivered a second discussion-based workshop, entitled “Functional Evidence Evaluation”. This report summarises the outcomes and participant opinion captured in the workshop.

In this report you will find;

- 1) Resources from the workshop content
- 2) Consensus opinion from the poll results
- 3) The future directions of the MAVE Education project

The participants

More than 92% of the participants indicated they were currently performing variant curation in the workshop polls. We believe that these results, collected from more than 68 curators, should be a good representation of the practicing fields opinion.

The Workshop Content

The MAVE Education Project is now continuing to work to share our learning materials more widely through collaboration with the Atlas of Variant Effects.

Slides

The workshop slides are now available via the Atlas of Variant Effects clinical application webpage. You can also find links to the current recommendations and guidelines for functional evidence and MAVE evaluation.

<https://www.varianteffect.org/clinical-application>

The Activities

At the Functional Evidence Evaluation workshop, we presented four variant-case based activities. Each activity discussed a particular functional assay and discussed how you might evaluate, determine evidence strength or apply this assay to a specific variant. These were presented as discussions, so that we could collate the opinion regarding the variant cases.

98% of participants would like to access the activities afterward. In response to this feedback, we have modified the activities to be online, self-directed and with answers supplied. Download the free public .pdf Instructional Slides from Zenodo and use the embedded links to access the activities. Click submit at the end of the activity to display the answers and feedback comments, and to contribute your answers to the research and development.

Online functional Evidence Evaluation Activities

Instructional Slides: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13888494>

Noting the activities remain part of the building research and are still in development. If any link does not work for you or you have any questions, concerns, or suggestions for improvements, please contact the MAVE Education Project coordinator, Dr Rehan Villani, rehan.villani@qimrberghofer.edu.au.

The LR calculator

In the workshop we presented a development version of the ENIGMA Likelihood Ratio Calculator. This was created, adapted and/or used by ENIGMA analytical working group members, primarily David Goldgar, Kyriaki Michailidou, Paul James and Amanda Spurdle for use in calibrating data types for ENIGMA research and ENIGMA contributions to Variant Curation Expert Panel activities.

89% of participants indicated they may use the LR calculator provided in the workshop to support their curation activities. Suggestions to improve the LR calculator were also requested, some suggestions were: added instructions, increased automation and more education/understanding in the background calculations. A barrier was identified around confidence in sample/controls used which may also need to be addressed to increase LR calculator/evidence calculation use.

Based on the feedback from this workshop we have updated the ENIGMA LR calculator, including instruction, and it is now available via Zenodo file share. This development release is accessible via the free open research resource platform Zenodo, <https://zenodo.org/records/13324450>. You will need to register your email and request access. We share this as a pre-publication learning tool, please be aware that this tool will be developed further, the most-up-to-date version will be available through this link. We are also taking comments and consultation in regards to the ENIGMA Likelihood Ratio Calculator, so if you have any questions or feedback please contact the MAVE Education Project coordinator.

Informing future practice

Evidence strength calculation

Only 65% of participants indicated they were comfortable with LR calculation, while 35% (20/57) were not. In addition, the 11% of participants that indicated they would not use the LR calculator, indicated this was due to a lack of confidence with the tool. The workshop also identified an additional tool, https://gwigginshinyapps.io/lr_shiny/, that can calibrate best performing assay categories and calculate the resulting category's likelihood ratios, Walker et al. 2023. 79% (46/58) of the workshop

participants expressed interest in this tool and/or further training on calibrating functional evidence. We will therefore aim to provide additional training on the LR tool and alternative calibration tools/approaches.

Supporting evaluation of published assays

To investigate methods to improve application of functional evidence, we asked the participants (majority were clinical curators) what they would like to see in publications on functional data to support their translation to evidence and application. The high level of responses indicate that curators believe it highly important to include defined control reference sets (89%) and a description of how the method is appropriate for the mechanism of disease in functional data publications (91%), and also that LR calculation and individual evidence levels should also be presented.

Figure 1. What would you like to see in a research publication to support a decision to apply functional evidence in curation? Participants were asked to indicate according to the indicated categories, multiple selections allowed.

During the workshop, we discussed which reference sets (control variant types) are appropriate for evaluating evidence strength. The example assays in the introduction material presented ClinVar variants as reference set controls, however a number of control types were presented within the activities and discussed. We surveyed opinion of appropriate controls via poll to all the participants. While the majority of participants indicated that the appropriate control reference set depended on the mechanism, ClinVar pathogenic, benign and common gnomAD variants were most supported as a source of reference set variants. Fewer participants (less than 15%) were comfortable with ClinVar 'likely strength' variants or assumed protein termination coding or synonymous variants as reference set.

Figure 2. Percentage of participants comfortable using the indicated variant types as the suggested assumed clinical controls.

These results show that curators would like to see specific and defined information regarding to the application of the functional data, and have clear preferences for the type of controls used for reference set variants.

Continuing discussion forum

91% (49/54) said they would be interested to join a functional evidence discussion forum. Based on this result we aim to initiate a functional evidence discussion forum, starting with consultation from those participating on intent and format.

We will explore the feasibility (and content) at an online forum launch meeting in October, open to all interested participants. Watch for an announcement of the forum, you can email rehan.villani@gimrberghofer.edu.au to register for the mailing list.

Overall outcomes

The functional evidence evaluation workshop was very well attended and the participants were very engaged, indicating the growing recognition of the importance of functional assays to the curation field, and the importance of community of practice to this field. Overall, the workshop showed an increased average confidence score after the workshop, relative to the confidence score taken prior.

The workshop has informed our continuing project substantially, see our future directions below. The feedback given, especially regarding links and activity length (too long) will be used for the next workshop and discussion forum, as we hope to continue to support the growing community of practice around functional evidence evaluation.

Future Directions

Based on the MAVE Education project activities so far, including the Functional Evidence Evaluation Workshop we will:

- Develop and share current and additional learning and practice resources for functional evidence evaluation
- Initiate a campaign for knowledge transfer between diagnostic curators and genetics researchers around best value functional evidence evaluation practices
- Initiate a discussion forum for the presentation and discussion of functional evidence evaluation, supporting a functional evidence evaluation community of practice.

Conclusion

Thank you to all of the participants in the Functional Evidence Workshop

We would like to thank you, the participants and members of the diagnostic genomics community, for your support and engagement. Your consultation is very helpful in guiding the direction of the MAVE Education project. If you have any questions on the activities of the MAVE Education project team, please contact Rehan Villani, Project co-ordinator, rehan.villani@gimrberghofer.edu.au.

References

Richards S, Aziz N, Bale S, Bick D, Das S, Gastier-Foster J, Grody WW, Hegde M, Lyon E, Spector E, Voelkerding K, Rehm HL; ACMG Laboratory Quality Assurance Committee. Standards and guidelines for the interpretation of sequence variants: a joint consensus recommendation of the American College of Medical Genetics and Genomics and the Association for Molecular Pathology. *Genet Med*. 2015 May;17(5):405-24. doi: 10.1038/gim.2015.30. Epub 2015 Mar 5. PMID: 25741868; PMCID: PMC4544753.

Brnich SE, Abou Tayoun AN, Couch FJ, Cutting GR, Greenblatt MS, Heinen CD, Kanavy DM, Luo X, McNulty SM, Starita LM, Tavtigian SV, Wright MW, Harrison SM, Biesecker LG, Berg JS; Clinical Genome Resource Sequence Variant Interpretation Working Group. Recommendations for application of the functional evidence PS3/BS3 criterion using the ACMG/AMP sequence variant interpretation framework. *Genome Med*. 2019 Dec 31;12(1):3. doi: 10.1186/s13073-019-0690-2. PMID: 31892348; PMCID: PMC6938631.

Walker LC, Hoya M, Wiggins GAR, Lindy A, Vincent LM, Parsons MT, Canson DM, Bis-Brewer D, Cass A, Tchourbanov A, Zimmermann H, Byrne AB, Pesaran T, Karam R, Harrison SM, Spurdle AB; ClinGen Sequence Variant Interpretation Working Group. Using the ACMG/AMP framework to capture evidence related to predicted and observed impact on splicing: Recommendations from the ClinGen SVI Splicing Subgroup. *Am J Hum Genet*. 2023 Jul 6;110(7):1046-1067. doi: 10.1016/j.ajhg.2023.06.002. Epub 2023 Jun 22. PMID: 37352859; PMCID: PMC10357475.